

**WASTE ETHYLENE VINYL ACETATE AS A BONDING ENHANCER FOR
BITUMINOUS ASPHALT CONCRETE**

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Abstract

Introduction: With improved access to transportation, roads play a vital role today. As a result, this subfield of Civil Engineering is crucial to the success of the industry, as improved transportation links directly to increased GDP. Asphalt concrete is widely used as a road paving material today. Many people choose to drive on asphalt roads because of the low maintenance costs and high levels of comfort they provide. Road users aren't the only ones who gain from asphalt's use in road building and maintenance.

Methods: This study determined the optimum mix design of waste EVA mixed bitumen that can be used in the overlay. This study is an experimental type of research that focuses on physical property and mechanical property test. It was done with a systematic process in gathering and measuring information on the variables were established to attained optimum mix design waste EVA mixed bitumen as a bonding enhancer for bituminous asphalt concrete mixed and conducted at the laboratory of DPWH-Ilocos Norte of 1st District Engineering Office, Laoag City, Ilocos Norte.

Results: Generally, findings of this study among the seven mixtures, mixtures A, B, and C are *acceptable* with regards to optimum mixed design of waste EVA mixed with bitumen for overlay on physical properties and mechanical properties based on the ideal values. It is considered *acceptable* since it is within the established ranges based on ASTM requirements be used as mix design of waste EVA mixed bitumen for overlay.

Conclusions: Bitumen's softening point met standards. However, the binder has poorer penetration and higher softening values, causing some mixes to fail the standard. The ASTM Standard Specification Test showed that waste EVA with asphalt cement met the minimum stability and flow requirements.

Keywords: Waste Eva, Experimental Design, Bitumen, Physical Properties, Mechanical Properties

Introduction

The importance of roads in modern society can't be overstated as they provide improved mobility for people, goods, and services (Berg & Ihlstrom, 2019). This makes the study of road construction and maintenance a crucial aspect of Civil Engineering. One of the most used paving materials for roads is asphalt concrete, which offers cost-effectiveness and comfort to road users. Asphalt concrete is made up of aggregates, binder, and filler, and can be used in the construction and maintenance of roads, parking lots, and even play and sports areas (Lima et al., 2020). The aggregates used in the mixture can be crushed rock, sand, gravel, or slag, and the binder is typically bitumen (Nanea, 2021).

Bitumen is the cementitious material that can be found in different forms, such as rock asphalt, natural bitumen, tar and bitumen a byproduct of oil. According to EAPA (2015), the average amount of bitumen used in asphalt is 5% by weight. Today the world's demand for bitumen accounts for more than 100 million tons per year (Loureiro et al., 2020). The high demand has led to the rapid decrease on the supply for resources used in production of bitumen. In order to cope up with the demand, manufacturers use recyclable materials like tires and PVCs as a partial replacement for bituminous binders.

Porto et al., (2019) suggested that the addition of natural or synthetic polymers to bitumen can enhance its properties. Plastic resins, the main base of plastics, are processed and transformed to fit specific needs. One of these types is Ethylene Vinyl Acetate or known EVA. According to UPC (United Plastic Components), this copolymer resin can be used in adhesives, sealants, and coatings (Marques et al., 2020). This flexible porous plastic material also has good barrier properties, low-temperature toughness, stress crack resistance, hot-melt adhesive waterproof properties, and resistance to ultraviolet radiation (Szlachetka et al., 2021).

In addition, according to the World Bank (2021), the Philippines is the 3rd top source of plastic leaking into oceans in the world, generating 2.7 million metric tons of plastic garbage each year, 521 thousand tons of which end up in the ocean and by recycling polymers like the EVA, wastes in the environment can be reduced.

The use of plastic materials has been growing all over the world in packing, automotive and industrial applications (Dybka-Stepien et al., 2021). This results in a great generation of urban and industrial waste that can be stored or eliminated. Likewise, one method of eliminating plastics is done by incineration, however, as the production of plastics involves the use of potentially harmful chemicals, the ashes produced may not always be acceptable in a landfill because of their potentiality to cause groundwater and soil pollution (Irvanian & Ravari, 2020).

In addition, waste ethylene vinyl acetate (EVAs) utilized by the footwear industries cannot be melted through direct heat because of its molecular chains and hence another recycling process is needed. Currently, 17 billion pairs of shoes are produced worldwide every year, and this creates an enormous amount of post-consumer (end-of-life) shoe waste that is currently being disposed of in landfill sites around the world (Perez & Trejo, 2022). Further, 190,400 *tons* of EVA waste are generating worldwide every year needing a large surface for placement and storage and generates great costs of management due to its long biodegradation (Folino et al., 2020).

With these arguments, this research study was intended to determine the physical and mechanical properties of waste EVA. The researcher has conducted series of mixtures of bituminous asphalt and waste EVA. Hence, to come-up with an optimum mix design of waste EVA mixed as bonding enhancer for asphalt concrete with bitumen

that will be used to overlay into road pavement. This will benefit the government in terms minimizing irresponsible discharges of plastic waste.

Methodology

Research Design. This research is an experimental type of study that focused on the physical property test and mechanical property test evaluating the performance of waste EVA as a bonding enhancer for bituminous asphalt concrete mixed. The purpose of the experimental research is to discover the best material to be used for mixing asphalt for road construction (Cristea et al., 2018).

Data Gathering Procedure. Data collection involves laboratory experiments and testing. First, the study used natural aggregates from a construction firm and supply stockpile yard and waste EVA from surrounding residences, rubbish yards, vehicle upholstery shops, and shoe-repair shops in Ilocos Norte. Aggregates were proportioned according to Grading A of Item 310, 2004 DPWH Standard Specifications for highways, bridges, and airports. Aggregates were cleaned with flowing water during preparation. DPWH Grade A sieving and ASTM aggregate weighing were done. Third, Waste EVA preparation and cutting. Hand-cutting waste EVA. melt EVA faster. The DPWH 1st District Office Laboratory melted waste EVA in an oven at 90oC to 120oC (Crawford, R.J. 2002). Finally, the study's mix design used weight percentage as proportion.

Procedures During the Experiments. Before mixing with asphalt cement, sample aggregates were heated to 171–191°C. Bitumen was heated to the required temperature for mixing waste EVA and bitumen. Waste EVA was added to bitumen at 177 °C and swirled until homogenous. After reaching temperature, combine aggregates and bitumen with waste EVA. Hot asphalt combined with leftover EVA was promptly poured in preheated molding cylinder. The molding cylinder was filled with half the mixture and preheated plungers. To extract the sample, the molds and plungers were cleaned and oiled.

With the bottom plunger in position and the molding cylinder supported momentarily on the two steel bars, the mixture was tamped twenty-five times in a preheated spatula, fifteen times to reduce honeycomb and ten times to compact. The rest of the mixture was promptly placed to the molding cylinder and tamped. The sample was compressed with 75 Marshall Hammer blows because it was meant for heavy traffic (Ahmed et al., 2014). Turned over and repeated after compression. To determine water weight, samples were immersed in water and weighed again. After drying, the samples were weighed again to establish their saturated dry unit weight.

Testing of Samples. Penetration test was conducted to determine the consistency of the bitumen based on ASTM D5 – Standard Test Method for the Penetration of Bituminous Materials. Specific Gravity Test was conducted to determine the specific gravity of the asphalt cement with the different percentages of waste EVA based on ASTM D1188 – Test Method for Bulk Specific Gravity and Density of Bituminous Mixtures. Moreover, a test was conducted to determine the Softening Point and Melting Point of the bitumen based on ASTM D36 – Test Method for Softening Point of Bitumen (Ring and Ball Apparatus).

Results and Discussion

After obtaining data and information from the experiments in this study, analysis and evaluation of data were performed.

Physical Properties of Waste Ethylene Vinyl Acetate. This section of the research study presents the physical properties of waste Ethylene Vinyl Acetate (EVA)

mixed with bitumen which is presented in Table 1. Penetration test is used to evaluate the consistency of bitumen. It is used as a measure to the suitability of bitumen for use under different climatic conditions and various types of constructions.

Table 1.
Physical Properties Waste EVA Mixed with Bitumen

Physical Properties	Mixture	Value	Descriptive Interpretation	Established Standard
Consistency (Penetration Test) Results (mm)	A	65.17	Passed	60-70
	B	62.50	Passed	
	C	61.17	Passed	
	D	54.67	Failed	
	E	54.67	Failed	
	F	50.67	Failed	
	G	48.17	Failed	
Melting Point (°C)	A	49.33	Passed	49-56
	B	49.90	Passed	
	C	50.17	Passed	
	D	53.17	Passed	
	E	52.67	Passed	
	F	52.67	Passed	
	G	52.33	Passed	
Specific Gravity	A	1.025	Passed	0.97-1.02
	B	1.010	Passed	
	C	1.004	Passed	
	D	0.971	Passed	
	E	0.965	Failed	
	F	0.932	Failed	
	G	0.919	Failed	
Viscosity (Softening Point) (°C)	A	49.50	Passed	49-56
	B	49.40	Passed	
	C	50.80	Passed	
	D	51.90	Passed	
	E	53.65	Passed	
	F	54.80	Passed	
	G	55.30	Passed	

Legend:

Penetration Test Result	60-70	Passed
Melting Point	49-56	Passed
Specific Gravity	0.97-1.02	Passed
Viscosity	49-56	Passed

Table 1 shows the result of the penetration test of the different proportion of bitumen with waste EVA. For a 60/70 grade bitumen penetration value means is in the range 60 to 70.

The data shows that results for mixture A, mixture B, and mixture C have the penetration values of 65.17 mm and 62.50 mm and 61.17 mm, respectively which passed the minimum required penetration value. While mixture D, mixture E, mixture

F and mixture G attained 54.67 mm, 54.17 mm, 50.67 and 48.17 mm respectively which didn't meet the required value for penetration test. The results also show that as the percentage of waste EVA increases, the penetration value decreases. It confirms the study of Sadeque and Patil (2014) that there is a general trend of decreasing penetration value with increase in polymer concentration in bitumen.

According to Rahman et al., (2019), Bitumen penetration grade 60/70 means the penetration value is in the range 60 to 70 at standard test conditions which is commonly used as a Paving Grade. Bitumen 60/70 is suitable for road construction and for asphalt pavements with superior properties. This type of bitumen is used in the manufacture of hot mix asphalt for bases, wearing courses and is mainly used in roads in mild regions.

EVA has a very strong structure-forming influence on bitumen. Penetration value changes most rapidly at 25 °C, which means the higher the concentration of copolymer and the content of the ester groups, the lesser the depth of a binder needle penetration. The result of the study of Nizamuddin et al., (2021) proved that EVA modified binder gives lower penetration value compared to neat bitumen. It also gives higher softening point value, and higher viscosity. Effect of Aging on EVA modified binder is within permissible limits.

Melting Point Test Results. Melting point test is used to determine the temperature of bitumen where all the crystallinity in the mixture and films are destroyed (Ma et al., 2016). Melting point is highly dependent on purity, it can also be used for evaluating the quality of substances. After conducting the melting point test on a 60/70 graded bitumen with different percentages of waste EVA, all mixtures are within the required range.

Hence, softening point is useful in the classification of bitumen's, as one element in establishing the uniformity of shipments or sources of supply, and is indicative of the tendency of the material to flow at elevated temperatures encountered in service. Softening point is determined by ring and ball apparatus.

Specific Gravity Test (Specific Gravity) Results. The specific gravity of a bitumen binder is a fundamental property frequently required as an aid in classifying binders for use in paving jobs and used in identifying the source of bitumen binder. Bitumen binder has specific gravity in the range of 0.97 to 1.02 based from ASTM D70-97.

Based on table 4, the result shows that mixture A, mixture B, mixture C and mixture D with the values of 1.025, 1.010, 1.004, and 0.971 respectively passed the minimum required specific gravity for a bitumen binder. However, mixture E, mixture F and mixture G failed to reach the minimum required range of specific gravity for a bitumen binder. The table confirms that the specific gravity value decreases significantly by modifying bitumen according to Bhargava et al., (2020).

Viscosity (Softening Point) Test Results. Softening test is used to determine the softening point of bitumen. Softening point indicates the temperature at which binders possess the same viscosity. Also, it is useful in the classification of bitumen as one element in establishing the uniformity, as well as to indicate the tendency of the material to flow at elevated temperatures.

On the viscosity (softening point) test result shows in Table 2. After conducting the softening test on a 60/70 graded bitumen with different percentages of waste EVA, all mixtures are within the required range of softening point. Data results show that as the percent of waste EVA increases, its softening point increases which supports the study of Ahmad and Mahdi (2015).

As stated by Honarmand et al., (2018), the viscous properties of bitumen at high temperatures are improved by adding recycled EVA copolymer in amounts that depend on bitumen penetration grade. Moreover, significant microstructural changes, related to the development of a polymer-rich phase, tend to occur in the bitumen as polymer concentration increased. These changes in microstructure have a significant influence on the flow behavior of the binder and on its in-service performance.

Furthermore, viscoelastic properties of a 60/70 penetration grade bitumen are improved when either a virgin EVA or a recycled EVA copolymer of similar vinyl acetate content are mixed with it. The risk of cracking at low temperatures and rutting at high temperatures are both reduced. Better viscoelastic features are obtained with the bitumen modified with recycled EVA probably due to the presence of carbon black, which acts like a filler in this material. Stability tests performed combining oscillatory flow and microscopy results disclose that blends with the higher polymer proportion (3%) are susceptible of phase separation after 24 hours of storage at 165 C, but 1% blends are stable for at least four days. A general evaluation of the results indicates that the performance of this bitumen as a binder for road pavement is particularly improved when 1% of recycled EVA or virgin EVA is added (Yan et al., 2020).

Moreover, EVA with a high content of vinyl acetate groups are somewhat inferior by softening temperature and extensibility to the compositions, modified by EVA with a low content of ester groups, because of the greater initial plasticity of the copolymer in the second case. It should be noted that the bitumen, modified by polymers, begin to acquire their properties and as several researchers noted, the standard bitumen test methods do not allow to reflect these changes completely. The rheological properties of bitumen are improved by means of EVA polymer modification. The semi crystalline EVA copolymer provides the modification of bitumen through the crystallization of rigid three-dimensional networks within the bitumen. Conventional penetration, softening point, ductility, and high temperature viscosity tests have demonstrated the increased stiffness (hardness) and improved temperature susceptibility of the EVA PMBs (Bulatovic et al., 2013).

Acceptability of Physical Properties to the Established Standard

Table 3 reflects the results of mixtures as to physical properties. As a result, there are mixtures which is considered “*acceptable*” based on the ASTM.

Viscosity (Penetration Test) Results. As a result, Mixture A, B, and C passed (PTR = 60 – 70mm) while mixture D, E, G and F failed. These indicate the data shows, the higher the percentage of EVA that can be mixed may fail.

Melting Point. As a result, all the mixtures were passed and have meet the standard requirements, 49-56(°C) as to melting point of the pure bitumen that can be used in overlay.

Specific Gravity. On the specific gravity, mixture A, B, C and D are considered passed, which means that they are within the established standard of pure bitumen, 0.97-1.02. On the other hand, mixture E, F and G are failed they have a below the value as to established standard.

Table 3
Acceptable Physical Properties based on ASTM

Mixture	Physical Properties			
	Consistency	Melting Point	Specific Gravity	Viscosity

A	65.17*	49.33*	1.025*	49.40*
B	62.50*	49.90*	1.010*	49.90*
C	61.17*	50.17*	1.004*	50.80*
D	54.67	53.17*	0.971*	51.90*
E	54.17	52.67*	0.965	53.65*
F	50.67	52.67*	0.932	54.80*
G	48.17	52.33*	0.919	55.30*

Legend:

Penetration Test Result	60-70	Passed
Melting Point	49-56	Passed
Specific Gravity	0.97-1.02	Passed
Viscosity	49-56	Passed

* - acceptable mixtures based on ASTM

Viscosity. All mixtures of the study are passed, this shows that they have are within the standard range from 49-56 °C. Hence, with the seven mixtures on different physical properties, the *acceptable* mixtures are mixture A, B, and C, which have attained the established standard.

Mechanical Properties Test on Marshall Stability and Flow Values of Waste EVA Mixed with Bitumen. As regards the mechanical properties test on Marshall Stability and Flow Values of Waste EVA that is being mixed with bitumen shows in Table 6.

Marshall Stability is the peak resistance load obtained during a constant rate of deformation loading sequence. It can also be defined as the load obtained, when the rate of loading increase begins to decrease, such that the curve starts to become horizontal. Flow is the measure of deformation of the specimen at failure and recorded either by the dial gauge or displacement cell attached to the breaking head.

Marshall Stability Test Result. The Marshall Stability Test Results is reflected in table 4. Results shows the average result of stability in pound force (lbf). All the design mix have passed the minimum stability of 1500 lbf of Marshall Design criteria for heavy traffic. Mixture F achieved the maximum stability which is equal to 2797.25 lbf.

Based on the table, the stability value increases with increasing percentage of waste EVA up to maximum, after which the value decreases. Therefore, it confirms the study of Kumar et al that as the additive content increases, the stability value increases initially, reaches a maximum and then decreases.

Flow Value Test. Table 4, it shows the average result of flow test on the bituminous binder of different percentages of waste EVA. It also shows that all the design mixed with waste EVA met the minimum criteria for the flow value, in which all results are within the lower limit of 8 mm and the upper limit of 16 mm. Mixture F achieved the highest value of flow equal to 11.45 mm.

Table 4.

Mechanical Properties Test-Marshall Stability and Flow Value

Mechanical Properties	Mixture	Value	Remarks	Established Standard
Marshall Stability (lbf)	A	2121.10	Passed	Minimum of 1500
	B	2249.22	Passed	
	C	2249.22	Passed	
	D	2365.83	Passed	
	E	2602.22	Passed	

	F	2797.25	Passed	
	G	2300.18	Passed	
	A	8.78	Passed	
	B	8.90	Passed	
	C	9.09	Passed	
Flow Test Values (mm)	D	9.53	Passed	8-16
	E	9.38	Passed	
	F	11.45	Passed	
	G	10.61	Passed	

Legend:

For Marshall Stability		Flow Test	
Min of 1500 lbf	Passed	8-16	Passed
below 1500 lbf	Failed	below 8	Failed
		above 16	Failed

Acceptability on Mechanical Properties as to Marshall Stability and Flow Value Test to the established standard. Table 5 shows the Mechanical Properties Test-Marshall Stability and Flow Test Value of waste EVA mixed with bitumen and Pure Asphalt Bitumen.

Marshall Stability

As table 5, all the mixtures have attained the value equal to 1500 lbf and even higher in values.

Table 5.
Mechanical Properties and Established Standard

Mixture	Mechanical Properties	
	Marshall Stability	Flow Value Test
A	2121.10*	8.78*
B	2249.22*	8.90*
C	2249.22*	9.09*
D	2365.83*	9.53*
E	2602.22*	9.38*
F	2797.25*	11.45*
G	2300.18*	10.61*

Legend:

For Marshall Stability		Flow Test	
Min of 1500 lbf	Passed	8-16	Passed
below 1500 lbf	Failed	below 8	Failed
		above 16	Failed

* - acceptable mixtures based on ASTM

Marshall flow is a measure of deformation (elastic plus plastic) of the asphalt mix determined during the stability test (ASTM D1559: Standard Test Method for Marshall Stability and Flow of Asphalt Mixtures). As the additive content increases, the stability value increases initially, reaches a maximum and then decreases (Kumar et. al, 2017).

Flow Value Test. All the mixtures have met the standard from 8-16mm on flow test values. Moreover, the flow test is used to measure the workability of high or very high workable concrete, which eventually would exhibit the collapse of slump. It gives an idea about the quality of concrete with respect to the consistency and cohesiveness. This workability test is quite simple to perform and is the best

for the concrete which has a nominal maximum size of aggregate less than 38 mm. Furthermore, all the mixtures have met the established standard based on ASTM on mechanical properties particularly in Marshall Stability and Flow Value Test.

Optimum mix design of waste EVA mixed with bitumen for overlay. The optimum mix design of waste EVA mixed bitumen was used in the overlay. For the optimum mix design of waste EVA mixed with bitumen for overlay is being presented in Table 6. On this table it presents the established standards. It may reflect in the table that there are mixtures who have passed or met the established standard into the other properties like mixtures D, E, F and G have not attained all the established standard in all the properties of physical and mechanical. Hence, as a result, it shows that among the mixtures being used by the researcher mixtures A, B, and C have attained the established standard.

Table 6

Optimum mix design of waste EVA mixed with bitumen for overlay

Mixture	Physical Properties				Mechanical Properties	
	Consistency	Melting Point	Specific Gravity	Viscosity	Marshall Stability	Flow Value Test
A	65.17*	49.33*	1.025*	49.40*	2121.10*	8.78*
B	62.50*	49.90*	1.010*	49.90*	2249.22*	8.90*
C	61.17*	50.17*	1.004*	50.80*	2249.22*	9.09*
D	54.67	53.17*	0.971*	51.90*	2365.83*	9.53*
E	54.17	52.67*	0.965	53.65*	2602.22*	9.38*
F	50.67	52.67*	0.932	54.80*	2797.25*	11.45*
G	48.17	52.33*	0.919	55.30*	2300.18*	10.61*

* - acceptable value based on ASTM

Conclusion

The results of this study have provided important insights into the physical properties of bitumen and waste EVA when used in combination for road construction. The researcher found that the softening point of the bitumen conformed to standard requirements, but the binder showed lower penetration values and higher softening values which resulted in some mixtures failing to meet the standards. However, the stability and flow value of the waste EVA with asphalt cement met the minimum requirements as specified in the ASTM Standard Specification Test. Based on the results, the researcher identified the optimum mixed design of waste EVA with bitumen, with mixtures A, B, and C being deemed acceptable as they met the established ranges according to the ASTM requirements. These findings provide valuable information for contractors, engineers, and government agencies in their use of waste EVA as a partial replacement of bitumen in asphalt.

Recommendation

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations have been formulated: (1) The utilization of waste EVA as a substitute for bitumen in asphalt construction and maintenance can be a cost-effective and environmentally friendly alternative, and its use can be beneficial to contractors, engineers, and government

agencies. This conclusion highlights the potential of waste EVA as a solution for reducing waste in the community. (2) Further research should be conducted on different waste materials to determine the best mixture for overlay. (3) Institutional extension programs should provide education and awareness on the proper utilization of waste materials to support solid waste management programs.

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